
Some publicly available spots of expertise in anti-corruption matters

Mladen Mladenov *¹ A

*Corresponding author: ¹ Dr of Political Science, Lecturer of Institutes, e-mail: mmladenov@abv.bg, ORCID: 0000-0002-1441-4488

^A Institute of Public Administration & Institute of Internal Auditors in Bulgaria, Sofia, Bulgaria

Received: September 1, 2021 | **Revised:** September 18, 2021 | **Accepted:** September 30, 2021

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6394940

Abstract

The publicly available spots of expertise in anti-corruption matters are these sources, which provides fast, true and authoritative Internet information in the field of anti-corruption. The article eyes at web-sites of Council of Europe – Group of States against Corruption (GRECO), Council of Europe, Network of Corruption Prevention Authorities (NCPA), The European Partners Against Corruption (EPAC), European Contact-Point Network Against Corruption (EACN), Network of European Integrity and Whistleblowing Authorities (NEIWA), The High Authority for Transparency in Public Life (HATPL), the Network for Integrity (NI), International Anti-Corruption Academy (IACA) and European Public Prosecutor's Office (EPPO). It is sustained that lawyers, academics, independent consultants, security experts, governmental officials, citizens and students have to know the sources of information about preventing and combating corruption. Categorically, the persons, occupied professions of confidence and security should be familiar with anti-corruption available information, because of legitimate expectation for their expertise, integrity and professional behavior, which is base of individual and public security.

Key words: anti-corruption, security, expertise, integrity, professions.

Introduction

Indisputably, in each society and state the efforts for counteracting corruption are extremely necessary to ensure the social binder and to prevent jeopardies for the public security. Inasmuch the criminals permanently develop their styles and modes for realization of corruption activities and results, there is a serious need for exchange of good practices and standards in anti-corruption problematics – and exactly this is the reason for the present research, which is trying to introduce in concise manner some of the most valuable sources of fast, true and authoritative Internet information in the field of anti-corruption. This work does not pretend to show all the relative public sources in electronic word with anti-corruption focus, but to bring to mind even sufficient number of them.

The task of the article is to facilitate the law-enforcement officers in the field of security and anti-corruption to available and useful information in one fast manner. Likewise, the academic society, especially the students in the fields of law, police, security and public administration studies will have a prompt manual for their learning and research.

Material and methods

The main method of the research is a view of the some publicly available spots of expertise in anti-corruption matters in Internet and their short presentation in the article with two main goals – their distinct indication and their supplementation of each other in the anti-corruption matters.

The proposed method of presentation of the Internet sources below is valuable for two main reasons – the concise view of information and the projection of the visible specialization of the different anti-corruption electronic platforms.

Discussion

About some important publicly available spots of expertise in anti-corruption matters

The significance of the results of this work is in concentration in one text of very important, technically quickly accessible, legal available, contemporary and good structured information in anti-corruption area, and for intelligible reasons there is no need of citations of already published literature.

Once more time – the sources below are only some among the very important and visible in the Internet space, specialized in anti-corruption matters and they are selected for the exposition in this work only for their professional significance and authoritative gravity for the academic and professional group of prospectors of such a specific information.

Nowadays with the potential of Internet any information is technical available, as long as it is already shared with the public. The good thing is that in the contemporary world the fundamental information is transparent for the audience. There is another question that the dangerous, sensitive and secret information is not communicated in publicity for security reasons.

These sources for useful information are nominated in the article as “Publicly Available Spots of Expertise in Anti-Corruption Matters” for the reason of their visibility and tangibility, as opposed to secret and operative information in hands of public prosecutors, police officers and functionary in national anti-corruption bodies, organizations, institutions and authorities, where concrete procedural information is protected by law and prohibited in principle for partaking with the broad publicity.

Categorically, the first and important spot in anti-corruption matters has to be the web-site of Council of Europe – Group of States against Corruption (Council of Europe, Group of States against Corruption). Therein is very guiding information as the narrative that GRECO was established by the Council of Europe to monitor States’ compliance with the organization’s anti-corruption standards. Moreover, its own objective is to improve the capacity of its members to fight corruption by monitoring their compliance with Council of Europe anti-corruption standards through a dynamic process of mutual evaluation and peer pressure. It also helps to identify deficiencies in national anti-corruption policies, prompting the necessary legislative, institutional and practical reforms.

But one among all the things is that GRECO provides a platform for the sharing of best practice in the prevention and detection of corruption, through conferences and other meetings, but also with some specific reports as “Report of the Independent Investigation Body on the allegations of corruption within the Parliamentary Assembly” and “Assessment of the Code of Conduct for Members of the Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe” (Council of Europe, Group of States against Corruption). Both in them are systematically regarded problems with conflict of interest; gifts and other benefits; incompatibility and accessory activities; post-employment restrictions; financial interests; contracts with state authorities; third party contacts and lobbying; misuse of confidential information and of public resources, et cetera.

Besides, into the Council of Europe there is Network of Corruption Prevention Authorities (NCPA), structured in Economic Crime and Cooperation Division (Council of Europe, Network of Corruption Prevention Authorities), which units efforts to improve the systematic collection, management and exchange of information among anti-corruption authorities, including their respective experiences and good practices; supports the members to enhance capacities and promote operational independence; recognizes and promotes international standards for the prevention of corruption; stimulates other international stakeholders for the promotion of integrity

In the political and legal space of the European Union (EU) there are many activities and information about them. For example, the specific issue of public procurement is highlighted always, but also in concrete (Report from the Commission to the Council). Ditto, ascertainment in this line is made: “Regulations and sanctions applicable to conflicts of interest vary across the EU. Some Member States have dedicated legislation that covers a wide range of elected and appointed public officials, as well as specialized agencies tasked to carry out checks. The level of scrutiny varies from one Member State to another: some have independent agencies that monitor conflicts of interest, but the capacity to cover these situations countrywide is limited and follow-up of their decisions is insufficient; others have an ethics commission in charge of such verifications that reports to

Parliament.

As they state by themselves in their web-site (European Partners against Corruption), The European Partners against Corruption (EPAC) and European contact-point network against corruption (EACN) are independent forums for practitioners, united in the common goal of preventing and combating corruption. Many useful documents might be discovered there, for instance: Manual on Preventing Corruption and Promoting Integrity; Integrity Risk Management Guideline; Setting Standards for Europe Handbook; Anti-Corruption Authority Standards; Police Oversight Principles; Handbook for Evaluating the Effectiveness of Police Oversight Bodies, and so on. Similarly, the declarations from the Annual Professional Conference are visible, as well as recommendations adopted by the General Assembly are shown.

The crimes from the group of corruption are hard to be proved from procedural legal point of view. That is why the whistleblowing is not only ethical, but highly respected legal value. There is also one very actual source – a Network of European Integrity and Whistleblowing Authorities (Network of European Integrity and Whistleblowing Authorities), where government organizations from various European countries have set up a network in which they work together and exchange knowledge in the field of whistleblowing and integrity. Namely this exchange of experience among national authorities and learning from each other is the main success of this professional lawfulness-oriented organizations.

Because by the definition, corruption must be lived and flourished only in public milieu (power and financial resources), there is a critical need the phenomena to be reviewed together. That is why one successful national approach must be shared here - The High Authority for Transparency in Public Life (The High Authority for Transparency in Public Life). Shortly, it aims at promoting public integrity in France. It also controls the integrity of the highest-ranking French public officials, who are required to disclose their assets and interests and manages a public register of lobbyists in order to provide information on key aspects of lobbying activities.

As its own web-site indicates, The Network for Integrity (The Network for Integrity) is currently comprised of 14 institutions from 14 different countries on 4 continents. Despite their different legal traditions, these institutions all share common values and perform tasks related to transparency, ethics and integrity of public officials. They perform all their duties without receiving instructions from political powers and hold non-jurisdictional statuses. To promote integrity, the Network has several objectives, including that of facilitating the exchange of information and of best practices among members. These exchanges are facilitated by the similarities in terms of goals and missions that exist between the different institutions.

One very professional and fast developed organization, which deserves special attention here is International Anti-Corruption Academy (International Anti-Corruption Academy), initiated by the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC), INTERPOL, the European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF), the Republic of Austria, and other stakeholders, nowadays with 80 Member States and organizations from around the world. The main point here is, that IACA has got 100% focus on anti-corruption and compliance education.

At the end, but not the last in significance, the very new European Public Prosecutor's Office (European Public Prosecutor's Office), which started its work on 1 June 2021, already has significant information on its web-site. There are categories about news, where some real contemporary cases of counteracting corruption are briefly described, as well in near future possibility for reporting a crime to the EPPO in detailed information is depicted in a comprehensible manner.

Conclusions

It might be maintained, that both the professionals (lawyers, academics, independent consultants, security experts, governmental officials, etc.) from one side, and laypeople (citizens and students) from another side, have to know exactly the sources of information above, because the highest standards of preventing and combating corruption must be followed in their dynamic development day-to-day. Especially the persons, occupied some among professions of confidence and security (for

example – auditors, accountants, secret-keepers, attorneys-at-law, and the rest of it) should be very familiar with them, because of highest expectation from the society for their integrity and law-abiding behavior, both the fundamentals for prevention of risks and assurance of individual and public security.

References

- Council of Europe, Group of States against Corruption (GRECO), [online]. [accessed December 10th, 2021]. Available from : <https://www.coe.int/en/web/greco>.
- Council of Europe, Network of Corruption Prevention Authorities (NCPA), [online]. [accessed December 10th, 2021]. Available from : <https://www.coe.int/en/web/corruption/ncpa-network>.
- European Partners against Corruption (EPAC) and European contact-point network against corruption (EACN), [online]. [accessed December 10th, 2021]. Available from : <https://www.epac-eacn.org/about>.
- European Public Prosecutor's Office (EPPO), [online]. [accessed December 10th, 2021]. Available from : <https://www.eppo.europa.eu/en/background>.
- International Anti-Corruption Academy (IACA), [accessed December 10th, 2021]. Available from : <https://www.iaca.int/who-we-are.html>.
- Network of European Integrity and Whistleblowing Authorities (NEIWA), [online]. [accessed December 10th, 2021]. Available from : <https://www.huisvoorklokkenluiders.nl/samenwerking/internationaal/europees-netwerk>.
- Report from the Commission to the Council and the European Parliament, EU Anti-Corruption Report, Brussels, 3.2.2014, COM (2014), 38 final, [online]. [accessed December 10th, 2021]. Available from : https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/system/files/2020-09/acr_2014_en.pdf.
- The High Authority for Transparency in Public Life (HATPL), [online]. [accessed December 10th, 2021]. Available from : <https://www.hatvp.fr/en/>.
- The Network for Integrity (NI), [online]. [accessed December 10th, 2021]. Available from : <https://networkforintegrity.org/the-network/>.